

**PEDAGOGICAL OPPORTUNITIES TO DEVELOP PROFESSIONAL
CREATIVE ABILITIES OF STUDENTS OF HIGHER EDUCATIONAL**

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Annotation:

This article describes the specific features of the development of professional creative abilities of students when using pedagogical opportunities and technologies.

Keywords: educational system, creative ability, professional pedagogy, technology, educational technologies, creativity.

**ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИЕ ВОЗМОЖНОСТИ РАЗВИТИЯ
ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНЫХ СПОСОБНОСТЕЙ СТУДЕНТОВ ВЫСШЕГО
УЧЕБНОГО ЗАВЕДЕНИЯ**

Аннотация

В данной статье рассмотрены особенности развития профессиональных творческих способностей студентов высшего учебного заведения педагогические возможности развития этих способностей у учащихся при использовании методов и технологий.

Ключевые слова: образовательная система, творческих способностей, профессиональная педагогика, технология, образовательные технологии, креативность.

**OLIJ TA'LIM MUASSASASI TALABALARINI KASBIY IJODIY
QOBILIYATINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING PEDAGOGIC
IMKONIYATLARI**

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Termiz davlat Pedagogika instituti**Ta'lim tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi 2-bosqich magistranti**

Annotatsiya

Ushbu maqolada Oliy ta'lim muassasasi talabalarini kasbiy ijodiy qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirishning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari pedagogic imkoniyatlari qanday usul va texnologiyalardan foydalanganda talabalarda bu qobiliyatlar rivojlanishi haqida yoritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: ta'lim tizimi, ijodiy qobiliyat, kasbiy pedagogika, texnologiya, ta'lim texnologiyalari, kreativlik.

The legal and normative basis for increasing the creative potential of students of higher educational institutions of our republic, developing professional and creative abilities, forming independent thinking skills, further improving the curriculum, program, and literature creation system was created, and the material and technical base of the educational system was developed. Tasks such as "increasing the level of coverage with higher education, training highly qualified, creative and systematic thinking personnel, able to make independent decisions based on international standards, creating the necessary conditions for the manifestation of their intellectual abilities and formation as a spiritually mature person" [1]. In this case, the conditions for the use of cognitive-informational, personal, cultural, competence paradigms in the development of professional and creative abilities of students, the implementation of diagnostics of the quality of teaching, the design of critical thinking and developmental educational technologies, the implementation of synergistic integration of higher education and production in the training of modern specialists will be expanded.

We emphasize a number of contradictions, on which the methodological part of the research is based, in accordance with the laws of dialectics, and which, in turn, determine the laws of the improvement of the individual.

The first conflict is that the individual's acquisition of knowledge and practical skills, improvement of his intellectual and moral powers is self-oriented, that is, the student is the only consumer of his labor until a certain time, while the subject and object of the process of developing professional and creative abilities. This conflict does not always serve as a conscious need for knowledge, development of skills and competencies for the student to competently fulfill future professional obligations. The majority of students do not sufficiently understand the importance and necessity of daily work, do not know how to correctly connect the current and final goals and tasks of study.

The resolution of this conflict is partially implemented by introducing amendments to the curricula and programs of the studied subjects, which are held annually during the discussions of the department's meetings, scientific councils of the faculties, and the scientific council of the institute. Also, the first conflict can be eliminated due to continuous work on self, which is carried out by students in cooperation with teachers.

The second conflict is the conflict between the desire of a student of a higher education institution to become a highly qualified teacher and the low level of development of personal emotional and volitional qualities. Its essence is that it is difficult to combine theoretical knowledge with the skills acquired in pedagogical practice due to the low level of emotional communication culture among students, which is considered a consequence of knowing how to empathize with children. The elimination of this conflict took place at the expense of continuous self-improvement of students in cooperation with the teaching staff of the higher education institution. In this case, the methods used in the study of psychological-pedagogical subjects are the most effective.

The second block is section training, in the organization of which teachers of the departments of pedagogy, psychology, ecology, physical education, pedagogy and methods of primary education take part, and they explain the problems that arise

in communication with students, and the organization of educational activities.

The third block of the meeting-seminar is the presentation of the "group business card", during the meeting student groups are divided into departments. The purpose of the performance of such a squad in front of the jury consisting of teachers participating in the meeting-seminar, their fellow students, all those who wish, and junior students is to demonstrate their preparation for summer pedagogic practice in summer health camps. The winners of the prizes during the performances on the stage are determined by the amount of the most points, in which artistic abilities, costumes, speech culture, mastery of musical tone, and the content of the performance are evaluated. Diplomas are also awarded to individual students who have demonstrated professional qualities. The evaluation by the jury allows to make corrections to the self-assessments of the learners, to guide future professional education teachers in the direction of self-improvement.

The third conflict is the conflict between the student's desire to fill his personal professional library, to familiarize himself with professional innovations, and insufficient socio-pedagogical and material and financial support for this. The solution to this conflict can be solved by increasing the volume and quality of independent educational and research work of students, increasing the level of professional and pedagogical culture, organizing scientific conferences, general meetings, and scientific sessions at the higher educational institution and other educational institutions.

Also, the third conflict can be resolved according to the financial support provided by the student union (financial assistance to the needy based on applications written to the union), the rectorate, district government (subsidies for student scholarships).

The fourth conflict is the conflict between the existing possibilities of professional and creative training and the insufficient development of ways of developing the professional and creative abilities of students of higher education institutions. This

conflict can be solved through creative research carried out by teachers of higher educational institutions, as well as through the creation of a scientifically based system of ways to develop the professional and creative abilities of students of pedagogical higher educational institutions, and the skills of teachers of higher educational institutions to ensure its introduction into the educational process.

The fifth conflict is between the constantly updated content and technology of methodical training of students and insufficient implementation in their teaching practice. The fifth conflict can be resolved on the condition that the entire team of teachers of the higher education institution and each individual teacher are ready to accept the innovation and introduce innovations into the educational process. It should be noted that a rational, thoughtful approach to choosing the optimal technology for training students with specific goals of education, updated processes of education and training, or new organizational forms of educational work is considered justified. Creating the illusion of change and progress, irregular innovative "inputs" are harmful and often undermine the foundation of an already fragile pedagogical system, leading to its deterioration.

The listed conflicts, of course, require their solution for the full development of professional and creative abilities of students of higher education institutions. Conflict resolution is more successful when teachers of higher education institutions, heads of relevant departments of higher education institutions, and other responsible persons ensure the creation of necessary conditions for this on the basis of active cooperation of students.

The scientific-pedagogical research conducted by us made it possible to consider in detail the little-studied area of the development of professional and creative abilities of students in the direction of goal-oriented and intensive approach to the professional ideal.

When introducing an innovative approach in pedagogy, it is possible to widely use such types of creative activity as spiritual, didactic, technological, and

organizational [2].

Spiritual creativity is a type of activity based on an unrepeatable, unique approach that gives new qualitative results in the spiritual and moral sphere among teachers and students.

Didactic creativity is a type of activity based on the selection and qualification of educational material, as well as the development of new directions of students' learning.

Technological creativity is a type of activity related to the search and creation of new systems, processes and situations that allow to achieve high results, and it is the most complex type of creativity that completely covers the activities of teachers and students. The uniqueness of this type of creativity is explained by the fact that it is aimed at transferring the elements of innovation to a specific technology, radically changing its effectiveness.

Organizational creativity is creativity in planning, control, allocation and mobilization of resources, communication with the external environment, creation of new methods of communication between students and the teacher, organization and management [3; p. 26].

Sh. Sharipov emphasized the formation of professional creativity in the following stages based on the experience of creativity:

Preliminary (formed during the implementation of the methods of work-movement indicated in the curriculum; as an example, on the basis of approximate actions: information about the execution of the skill is required).

Analytical (actions are performed separately, a comprehensive emotional analysis of the actions to be performed is carried out).

Synthetic (actions performed separately are repeated in a generalized state and a general image of actions is formed).

Automation (redundant actions are eliminated, attention shifts from the activity process to the result) [3].

Vocational fitness is not only a record of the fitness or unfitness of this person to perform labor duties in this profession, of course. Professional suitability in other ways:

- 1) whether a person is suitable for his chosen profession or not;
- 2) what he should follow when choosing a life path;
- 3) it should be considered from the point of view of how to approach the issue of its education in a reasonable way, that is, how to form, educate and develop professional aptitude in it in an extremely appropriate way [4; pp. 39-40].

To develop as a specialist, it is necessary to pay attention to a number of issues:

- conscious choice of profession;
- setting a clear goal for acquiring a profession;
- that the ideas about the profession are not far from real life;
- to be able to imagine the difficulties encountered in practical activities as well as the positive aspects of the occupation;
- formation of professional motives based on personal needs, not under the influence of foreign scientists;
- good knowledge of the social prestige and value of the profession;
- realizing that it takes a long time to grow as a specialist, etc. [5; p. 151].

N.A.Muslimov, K.M.Abdullaeva, O.A.Kuysinov, N.S.Gaipova, N.N.Karimova, M.Kodirov studied the technology of formation of professional competence of vocational education teachers, while A.I.Avazboev studied labor and vocational education teachers based on the integration of the content of educational subjects. dealt with issues of improvement of training [6, 7].

B.A. Akbarov's research analyzed the pedagogical system of formation of professional thinking among general secondary school students [8].

A. J. Allambergenov conducted research on issues of development of professional and technological competence among general secondary school students [9].

It was found that every teacher of a higher education institution can find and

recommend a number of resources to his students, and the use of their opportunities allows students to significantly enrich their pedagogical arsenal and professional-creative culture.

Professional pedagogical activity is so diverse and multifaceted that it is impossible to successfully engage in this activity without having certain personal qualities and characteristics. Therefore, the problem of searching for effective methods of formation and development of professional and creative abilities of students of pedagogical educational institutions, chosen by us, has arisen objectively and requires its own solution.

References:

1. O'zbekiston Respublikasi oliy ta'lim tizimini 2030 yilgacha rivojlantirish kontsepsiyasini tasdiqlash to'g'risida. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining PF-5847-son Farmoni. 2019 yil 8 oktyabr.
2. Spirin L.F. Professiogramma obщepedagogicheskaya. – M.: 1997 – 34 s.
3. Sharipov Sh.S. O'quvchilar kasbiy ijodkorligi uzviyligini ta'minlashning nazariyasi va amaliyoti.: Avtoref. dis. ... ped. fan. dok. – Toshkent.: TDPU, 2012. – 27 b.
4. Sharipov Sh.S., Davlatov K., Nasriddinova G.S. Kasbga yo'naltirishning ilmiy-pedagogik asoslari. O'quv qo'llanma. – Toshkent, 2007. – 146 b.
5. Qurbonov B., Muxliboev M., Qurbonova G. Mehnat ta'limini o'qitish metodikasi, kasb tanlashga yo'naltirish fanidan mehnat ta'limi yo'nalishi talabalari uchun o'quv-qo'llanma. – Guliston, 2013. – 295 b.
6. Avazboev A.I. O'quv predmetlari mazmunini integratsiyalash asosida mehnat va kasb ta'limi o'qituvchilarini tayyorlashni takomillashtirish: Dis. ... ped. fan. nom. – T., 2001. – 150 b.
7. Muslimov N.A., Abdullaeva K.M., Kuysinov O.A., Gaipova N.S., Karimova N.N., Kodirov M. Kasb ta'limi o'qituvchilarining kasbiy kompetentliginishakllantirish texnologiyasi. – T.: Fan va texnologiya, 2013. –128

b.

8. Akbarov B.A. Umumiy o'rta ta'lim maktabi o'quvchilarida kasbiy tafakkurni shakllantirishning pedagogik tizimi.: Avtoref. dis. ... ped. fan. bo'yicha fal. dok. – Namangan, 2020. – 52 b.

9. Allambergenov A.J. Umumiy o'rta ta'lim maktabi o'quvchilarida kasbiy-texnologik kompetentlikni rivojlantirish.: Avtoref. dis. ... ped. fan. bo'yicha fal. dok. – Nukus, 2020. – 52 b.